

Original Research

Impact of Self-Directed Career Attitude on Employee Job Satisfaction: Mediating Role of Leadership

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Abstract

The self-directed career attitude encompasses the willingness to take ownership and control of one's career path and actively steer one's professional growth and advancement. The present study aims to investigate the influence of self-directed career attitude (SDCA) on employee job satisfaction (EJS). This study additionally investigates the mediating function of leadership in the relationship between self-directed career attitude (SDCA) and employee job satisfaction (EJS). Four hypotheses were formulated in order to examine both the direct and indirect connections. The primary data was obtained by administering a questionnaire and then analyzed using partial least squares structural equation modeling. The demographic information was analyzed using the statistical package for the social sciences. The theoretical framework employed in this study was self-determination theory. The test results indicate a significant positive correlation between SDCA, leadership, and EJS. The findings also suggest a noteworthy positive mediating influence of leadership in the relationship between SDCA and EJS. This study aims to enhance our understanding of the causes and outcomes of human behavior on human resources, hence playing a crucial role in facilitating efficient career management and formulating suitable HR policies.

Keywords: Employee job satisfaction, leadership, protean career attitude, self-directed career attitude.

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Introduction

A career can be defined as the ongoing process of professional growth and advancement that an individual undergoes, involving a series of employment positions, responsibilities, and encounters over their occupational trajectory. Career development is a series of successive roles, occupations, and pursuits undertaken over time, typically within a particular domain or sector, to attain personal satisfaction, economic security, and actualize one's vocational ambitions. A career is characterized by the ongoing cultivation of skills, knowledge, and competence, and it may entail navigating through various transitions, advancements, and adaptations in order to address evolving conditions and objectives. A career serves as the principal source of financial sustenance for most individuals, affording them the ability to provide for their own well-being and that of their families. The achievement of financial stability, which is facilitated by a prosperous professional trajectory, empowers individuals to fulfill their fundamental necessities, follow individual aspirations, and strategize for forthcoming endeavors.

A career extends beyond financial support, as it significantly influences multiple dimensions of an individual's personal and professional well-being. A satisfying professional trajectory enables individuals to partake in employment congruent with their interests, values, and passions. The experience of deriving significance and contentment from one's occupation can positively impact an individual's holistic happiness and well-being. The attainment of a prosperous professional trajectory plays a pivotal role in fostering the establishment and consolidation of a robust professional persona. Accomplishing advancements and acknowledgments within a particular domain can enhance an individual's sense of self-worth and standing internally within their business and externally within the wider professional sphere.

A profession provides opportunities for progression and development. Through a combination of commitment and exertion, individuals have the ability to advance to positions of greater authority, assume additional obligations, and avail themselves of novel prospects and trials. In order to succeed in a professional setting, individuals must be able to effectively navigate and respond to dynamic conditions, incorporate emerging technologies, and stay abreast of growing trends within their respective industries. This promotes the development of resilience and the capacity to navigate obstacles effectively. A profession is a vital element of an individual's existence that profoundly impacts their overall welfare, sense of direction, economic security, personal development, and involvement in society. The process encompasses the exploration of one's own identity, learning new abilities, and continuous personal growth, ultimately exerting a significant influence on an individual's life trajectory. There exists a range of career theories encompassing both classic and current perspectives. The protean career is a concept that encompasses two dimensions, one of which is known as the SDCA.

SDCA refers to an individual's proactive and empowered approach to directing their career path, development, and decision-making. Individuals exhibiting SDCA demonstrate proactive behavior by taking initiative, establishing personal objectives, and actively pursuing avenues for personal growth and professional progression. A notable

degree of independence, introspection, and accountability in determining one's career path defines this disposition.

Individuals who possess an SDCA demonstrate a sense of responsibility and accountability for their work choices and decisions. Individuals do not exclusively depend on external direction but exercise their discernment to make well-informed decisions under their unique values and objectives. Individuals exhibiting SDCA continuously learn actively pursue educational opportunities in order to augment their abilities and expand their knowledge. Individuals are willing to engage in novel experiences and pursue opportunities for training and education that facilitate their advancement in their respective professional domains. Individuals evaluate options, assess risks, and make choices by comprehensively grasping their skills and interests. These individuals demonstrate proactive behavior by actively pursuing opportunities for personal and professional success and acquiring new skills. Rather than passively waiting for possibilities to arise, they proactively generate opportunities. SDCA entails assuming responsibility for one's professional development, actively pursuing avenues for growth, and making decisions consistent with individual aspirations and principles. The concept enables individuals to effectively navigate their professional trajectory with autonomy, purpose, and resilience.

In western society, the idea of PCA has arisen, and a lot of study has been conducted there. There aren't many empirical studies looking at these new constructs in Asian contexts (Iqbal, Li, Yang, & Sindhu, 2022). These ideas were previously discussed in relation to performance and corporate behavior. Additionally, there was no study available to test the aforementioned theory in the context of SMEs. The SDCA scale was created in 2006, and it is necessary to test such occurrences in various organizational and cultural contexts. Given the foregoing information, the main goal of this study is to analyze the SDCA in relation to EJS and leadership. It also examines the mediating function of leadership between SDCA and EJS.

The Self-Determination Theory (SDT) and the notion of an SDCA exhibit a convergence of core ideas. Both theories highlight the significance of autonomy, intrinsic motivation, and personal agency in influencing an individual's behavior, encompassing their attitude toward career growth and decision-making. SDT is a psychological framework that Deci and Ryan (1985) formulated. This study aims to comprehend individuals' motivation and conduct by examining three fundamental psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The SDCA exhibits a strong correlation with the ideas of SDT, specifically regarding the concepts of autonomy and intrinsic drive. SDT significantly focuses on autonomy and personal choice in making professional decisions. Individuals with this mindset proactively navigate their professional trajectories by considering their personal preferences, strengths, and objectives, aligning with the autonomy requirement in SDT. Individuals with an SDCA frequently have a strong internal drive to pursue their professional aspirations. Individuals derive happiness and delight from establishing and attaining their goals, which resembles the concept of intrinsic motivation highlighted by SDT. Both SDT and the SDCA emphasize the importance of personal agency, empowerment, and intrinsic motivation in influencing human behavior. An SDCA is congruent with the tenets of SDT, as individuals who assume responsibility for their career trajectories are more inclined to encounter

contentment, psychological well-being, and a sense of accomplishment in their vocational endeavors.

This study aims to examine the direct influence of SDCA on employee job satisfaction and leadership. Additionally, this study investigates the mediating effect of leadership on the relationship between SDCA and EJS. Four hypotheses have been suggested to investigate the link mentioned above.

Literature Review

SDCA and EJS

EJS pertains to the favorable emotional state and general satisfaction employees derive from their employment, workplace conditions, and organizational affiliation. The aspect above holds significant importance as it has the potential to influence productivity, staff retention, and overall organizational success. Satisfaction among employees has been found to correlate positively with their level of engagement and motivation, ultimately resulting in enhanced job performance and productivity. According to Locke (1976), employees who experience satisfaction are more inclined to exert more effort to attain their objectives and contribute to the firm. Individuals are more motivated to remain within the business (Hulin, 2014). Individuals cultivate a sense of loyalty and attachment, resulting in an increased probability of remaining affiliated with the organization and making constructive contributions to its cultural milieu (Meyer & Allen, 1997).

The correlation between EJS and SDCA is intricately interconnected and reciprocally reinforcing. Both notions significantly enhance an individual's holistic well-being, level of engagement and overall success within an organizational context. Individuals who possess an SDCA exhibit inherent motivation in pursuing professional aspirations. Individuals derive satisfaction and happiness from their proactive engagement in professional growth. There is a strong correlation between intrinsic motivation and job happiness. When employees are actively involved in tasks that are congruent with their interests and passions, there is a higher likelihood of them experiencing job satisfaction and a heightened sense of purpose. The relationship between SDCA and employee job satisfaction is intertwined due to their shared focus on autonomy, intrinsic motivation, personal development, and alignment with individual values and objectives. Organizations that cultivate a conducive atmosphere wherein employees are empowered to assume responsibility for their professional growth and actively contribute are more inclined to have contented, motivated, and high-achieving personnel.

The concept of autonomy grants individuals the ability to exert control and possess ownership over their work, thereby augmenting their job satisfaction (Hackman & Oldham, 1976). Employees who are content and actively participate in SDCA are more inclined to undergo personal development and achieve higher levels of job satisfaction (Judge, Thoresen, Bono, & Patton, 2001). According to Chughtai and Buckley (2019), individuals are more likely to feel well-being, specifically work satisfaction, when their career choices align with their beliefs and ambitions. The present meta-analysis investigates the relationship between work satisfaction and employee turnover. According to Ng, Feldman, and Butts (2014), employees who are actively involved in

their work and have a sense of SDCA are more inclined to experience job satisfaction and exhibit a solid dedication to their respective businesses. Consequently, this heightened level of engagement and commitment diminishes the likelihood of turnover intentions among these individuals.

EJS is a significant determinant that has influence over multiple dimensions within a company, encompassing performance, retention, commitment, and the overall well-being of employees. Organizations that prioritize cultivating and nurturing a pleasant work environment that is favorable to enhancing job satisfaction are more likely to experience the advantages of increased employee engagement and overall organizational success. Consequently, the subsequent hypothesis was formulated:

H₁: SDCA has a positive impact on EJS

SDCA and Leadership

Leadership can be defined as the systematic exertion of influence, guidance, and direction over individuals or groups with the ultimate objective of attaining a shared purpose or vision. The task at hand encompasses encouraging, inspiring, and assisting individuals to engage in collaborative and efficient work. Leadership is a multifaceted concept that involves a diverse array of behaviors, talents, and qualities. These attributes collectively empower an individual, referred to as a leader, to effectively provide guidance, make informed decisions, and influence the actions and attitudes of their followers. Effective leadership encompasses more than just advising others; it also entails leading by example through one's behavior, communication, and adherence to ethical principles. The factor above plays a pivotal role in facilitating organizational success, instigating transformative processes, and cultivating a conducive work atmosphere.

The correlation between leadership and an SDCA is intricately connected since proficient leaders frequently foster and assist their team members in assuming responsibility for their career advancement. Influential leaders establish a conducive atmosphere where individuals can take ownership of their career trajectories. According to Sosik and Cameron (2010), a leadership style characterized by supportiveness fosters an environment where individuals are motivated to take the initiative and be proactive in their professional development. Transformational leaders can inspire and encourage followers, establishing a climate conducive to personal growth and development. This phenomenon can foster a proactive and autonomous orientation toward professional progression (Judge & Piccolo, 2004). Leaders who actively participate in coaching and mentorship activities assume a crucial role in guiding the professional advancement of their employees. Leaders of this nature play a vital role in enabling individuals to engage in self-directed learning and personal development (Clutterbuck, 2014).

In brief, the impact of leadership on individuals' self-directed career views is substantial, as it encompasses the provision of support, inspiration, and guidance. Leaders that effectively promote personal growth, autonomy, and development play a significant role in cultivating a self-directed approach to career management within their team members. Therefore, the subsequent hypothesis was formulated:

H₂: SDCA has a positive impact on leadership

Leadership and EJS

Organizational research has extensively studied and established the correlation between leadership and employee work satisfaction. The degree of job satisfaction that employees experience directly depends on applying effective leadership strategies. Leaders who demonstrate helpful, positive, and polite behaviors tend to foster a more positive work climate. This phenomenon, in turn, leads to increased levels of employee job satisfaction (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Moorman, & Fetter, 1990). Leaders who effectively communicate, offer constructive comments and actively engage employees in the decision-making process foster an environment characterized by transparency and empowerment. This phenomenon enhances employees' job happiness by promoting feelings of being appreciated and well-informed (Eisenbeiss, Van Knippenberg, & Boerner, 2008).

In essence, implementing leadership strategies significantly impacts how happy employees are at work. Leaders that demonstrate supportive, pleasant, communicative, and appreciative behaviors have been found to cultivate a work atmosphere that is more fulfilling, leading to increased levels of employee engagement and satisfaction. Therefore, the subsequent hypothesis was formulated:

H₃: Leadership has a positive impact on EJS

The mediating role of leadership

The present study posits that leadership is mediating between SDCA and EJS. This implies that leadership behaviors are an intermediary variable affecting the relationship between SDCA and employees' overall job happiness. But, how leadership is exercised can either improve or impede the connection between an individual's self-determination, competence, and relatedness and overall degree of pleasure with their job. This study investigates the progression of leader-member exchanges over a period of time, highlighting the influence of leadership and personality on the formation of these relationships, which subsequently affect the level of job satisfaction experienced by employees (Nahrgang, Morgeson, & Ilies, 2009).

Employee job satisfaction is defined as the general sense of happiness and positive emotional well-being that employees perceive within their work setting (Judge et al., 2001). The impact of leadership behaviors, such as supportive, transformative, or empowering leadership, on the relationship between an individual's self-directed career attitude and employee work satisfaction has been explored by Avolio, Gardner, Walumbwa, Luthans, and May (2004).

In brief, leadership plays a crucial role in mediating the relationship between employees' SDCA perspectives and their levels of job satisfaction. Implementing effective leadership techniques can cultivate a conducive climate that fosters and amplifies the favorable influence of self-directed career attitudes on employees' overall

satisfaction with their job and organizational encounters. Therefore, the subsequent hypothesis was formulated:

H₄: Leadership plays a mediating role between SDCA and EJS

Figure 1. Conceptual model

Methodology

Sampling

The research sample consists of individuals working in Pakistan's small and medium-sized firms (SMEs). The study's ideal sample size was determined to be 170 by utilizing G power analysis. In order to minimize the impact of sampling error, the researchers collected data from a sample of 250 people. The sample utilized in this research was determined to indicate the overall population, exhibiting a reliability coefficient of 0.90 and demonstrating consistent answers across all parameters

Data collection procedure

The data were gathered from participants using an online survey methodology. A total of 250 people were included in the study, from which 180 valid responses were collected. The research encompassed 110 male participants, accounting for 61% of the total, and 70 female participants, comprising 39% of the total. The study encompassed a sample size of 180 participants, who were classified into several age groups. Specifically, 22 individuals (12%) fell into the category of being under 25 years old; 91 individuals (51%) were between the ages of 26 and 35; 48 individuals (27%) were between the ages of 36 and 45; and 19 individuals (10%) were over the age of 45. This study investigated the distribution of career levels among several job roles: supervisor/worker, middle management, manager, and owner/CEO. The sample consisted of 10 persons (6%) in the supervisor/worker position, 122 individuals (68%) in middle management, 46 individuals (25%) in the manager position, and 2 individuals (1%) in the owner/CEO position. The participants possessed varying levels of educational attainment, including

basic/secondary (8), undergraduate (74), master's (96), and doctorate (2) degrees. The proportions corresponding to these degrees were 4%, 41%, 54%, and 1%, respectively. Table 1 displays demographic disparities and diverse population attributes.

Table 1. Respondents' characteristics

Respondents characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Men	110	61
Women	70	39
Total	180	100
Age group		
Under 25	22	12
26-35	91	51
36-45	48	27
Over 45	19	10
Total	180	100
Education		
Secondary or Basic	8	4
Undergraduate	74	41
Masters	96	54
PhD	2	1
Total	180	100
Position		
Supervisor/ Worker	10	6
Middle Manager	122	68
Manager	46	25
Owner/ CEO	2	1
Total	180	100

Measures

Data on SDCA, leadership, and EJS were collected using standardized measures. This study's foundation for evaluating SDCA was the 8-item PCA scale that Briscoe, Hall, and DeMuth (2006) developed. The Likert scale employed in this research goes from 1 (limited) to 5 (great). Chaiprasit and Santidhiraku (2011) created the leadership scale, and it served as the basis for the data collection for this study. The participants' replies were evaluated utilizing a Likert scale of five points, where a score of 1 indicates "strongly disagree" and a score of 5 indicates "strongly agree." The four items that comprise the EJS scale adopted from the previous study of Butt, Chohan, Sheikh, and Iqbal (2019), based on Bamfo, Dogbe, and Mingle (2018) research, assess various aspects of EJS.

Research methods

This is quantitative research that collects data from respondents utilizing convenient random sampling on a closed-ended questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale. PLS-SEM was used in this study to test the theoretical model. PLS-SEM provides a statistically

accurate evaluation based on a bootstrapping procedure that produces standard errors for route coefficients (Iqbal et al., 2022; Preacher & Hayes, 2008). A measurement model and then a structural model were used in a two-step analysis of the research model (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2010; Henseler, Ringle, & Sinkovics, 2009).

Results and discussion

The researchers utilized partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) as the chosen method for conducting data analysis. According to Haenlein and Kaplan (2004), the authors assert that PLS-SEM is a more favorable approach compared to other conventional multivariate methods. PLS-SEM is a statistical technique that offers a robust analysis using a bootstrapping procedure. This approach generates standard errors for route coefficients, enabling researchers to assess the significance of their findings (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2013; Nitzl, Roldan, & Cepeda, 2016; Preacher & Hayes, 2008). In the beginning, a number of assumptions were assessed, such as multicollinearity, normality, and common method variance (Tabachnick, Fidell, & Ullman, 2007). Hair, Black, Babin, and Anderson (2010) utilized a two-step methodology encompassing measurement and structural models to examine and interpret the collected data.

Measurement model assessment

In order to analyze the measurement model, it is imperative to evaluate each concept's reliability, internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant validity (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010; Henseler et al., 2009). PLS-SEM was employed in this study owing to its extensive recognition and adoption by researchers across several academic fields. The suitability of this study is attributed to its innovative approach to establishing criteria for rigorous data analysis (Hair, Risher, Sarstedt, & Ringle, 2019). The researchers employed factor loading to evaluate each individual item's dependability (Duarte & Raposo, 2010; Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Mena, 2012; Hulland, 1999). Hair et al. (2019) state a minimum threshold of 0.7 or above is necessary. Table 2 illustrates that all of the outside loadings in our study meet the established criteria.

Table 2. Factor loadings and variance inflated factor

Construct	Item	Loading	VIF
Self-directed Career Attitude	SDCA1	0.792	2.097
	SDCA2	0.823	2.444
	SDCA3	0.842	3.639
	SDCA4	0.857	3.162
	SDCA5	0.838	2.679
	SDCA6	0.791	2.318
	SDCA7	0.798	2.837
	SDCA8	0.791	2.397
EJS	EJS1	0.834	1.689
	EJS2	0.828	2.112

Construct	Item	Loading	VIF
	EJS3	0.814	2.099
	EJS4	0.775	1.640
Leadership			
	L1	0.739	1.855
	L2	0.777	2.183
	L3	0.804	2.485
	L4	0.722	1.841
	L5	0.774	2.208
	L6	0.727	2.002
	L7	0.755	2.161
	L8	0.753	2.132
	L9	0.847	3.154
	L10	0.803	2.453
	L11	0.825	2.798

*Note: VIF = Variance Inflated Factor

Internal consistency

Researchers frequently use composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha to determine the internal consistency of an instrument. The measurements commonly employ a minimum threshold of 0.70, as indicated by several studies (Bagozzi, Yi, & Phillips, 1991; Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2011; Hair et al., 2019; Joseph F Hair Jr, Hult, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2016). The internal consistency and reliability of the structures are presented in Table 3, as reported by Bagozzi et al. (1991). The variance inflated factor (VIF) is a statistical measure used to evaluate the presence of method bias and collinearity effects. According to Ringle, Wende, and Becker (2015), it is generally advised to consider a threshold of 5 or below for the VIF, as indicated in Table 3.

Table 3. Mean, SD, CA, CR, and AVE

Constructs	Mean	SD	CA	CR	AVE
SDCA	3.15	0.88	0.929	0.941	0.667
EJS	3.16	0.89	0.831	0.886	0.661
Leadership	3.19	0.86	0.934	0.943	0.602

SD, standard deviation; CA, Cronbach alpha; CR, composite reliability; AVE, average variance extracted.

The convergent and discriminant validity assessment is conducted by utilizing the average variance extracted (AVE), as proposed by Fornell and Larcker (1981). Convergent validity is commonly established by a minimum threshold of 0.5 or above (Chin, 1998). The findings pertaining to convergent validity are presented in Table 3. Table 3 illustrates that all latent variables exhibited average variance extracted (AVE) values that exceeded the predetermined cutoff point. According to Table 4, the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) was found to be greater than the correlations observed among the latent components. The current study demonstrates acceptable discriminant validity across all dimensions.

Table 4. Discriminant validity

Constructs	EJS	Leadership	SDCA
EJS	0.813		
Leadership	0.701	0.776	
SDCA	0.730	0.721	0.817

Structural model assessment

The R² coefficient measures the predictive capacity of the model (Sarstedt, Ringle, Henseler, & Hair, 2014). Chin (1998) proposed specific thresholds for interpreting the R² value, categorizing an R² value of 0.60 as vital, 0.33 as moderate, and 0.19 as weak. Table 5 presents the R² and Q² values pertaining to the EJS and leadership variables. The coefficient of determination (R²) for the EJS variable is 0.596, whereas for the leadership variable, it is 0.519. The Q² value obtained for EJS is 0.374, while the Q² value for leadership is 0.299. The F² values obtained for the leadership constructs (0.158) and SDCA (0.260) provide evidence supporting the validity of our study model.

Table 5. Predictive Relevance and Model Fit

Constructs	Q ²	R ²	F ²
EJS	0.374	0.596	
Leadership	0.299	0.519	0.158
SDCA			0.260

The research utilized the bootstrapping method, specifically employing 5,000 bootstrap samples, to evaluate the statistical significance of the hypothesis (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2010; Hair et al., 2011; Joe F Hair Jr, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & Kuppelwieser, 2014; Henseler et al., 2009). The findings from Table 6 and Figure 2 offer empirical support for Hypothesis 1 (H1), which posits a significant and positive association between SDCA and EJS ($\beta = 0.467$, $t = 7.527$, $p = 0.000$). Therefore, the hypothesis H1 has been confirmed.

The study's results supported Hypothesis 2, as they demonstrated a statistically significant association between SDCA and leadership ($\beta = 0.721$, $t = 21.118$, $p = 0.000$). The coefficients $\beta = 0.365$, $t = 5.738$, and $p = 0.000$ support hypothesis 3. The study's findings supported the notion that leadership plays a mediating role in the association between SDCA and EJS. The analysis findings revealed a statistically significant result ($\beta = 0.263$, $t = 5.800$, $p = 0.000$), providing evidence supporting partial mediation, as Baron and Kenny (1986) proposed.

Table 6. Structural model

Hypothesis	Relationship	Beta	SE	t-Value	p-Value	Decision
H1	SDCA → EJS	0.467	0.062	7.527	0.000	Supported
H2	SDCA → Leadership	0.721	0.034	21.118	0.000	Supported
H3	Leadership → EJS	0.365	0.064	5.738	0.000	Supported
H4	SDCA → Leadership → EJS	0.263	0.045	5.800	0.000	Supported

Figure 2. Hypothesis results

Discussion

The primary objective of this research was to examine the direct and indirect impacts of SDCA on EJS, with a specific focus on the mediating role of leadership. The findings suggest a robust correlation between SDCA and EJS. The results of this study support prior research that suggests PCA professionals yield advantages for both their employers and themselves (Iqbal et al., 2022). A positive correlation exists between a high SDCA, robust organizational identification, and a heightened sense of stewardship toward the organization's success. Furthermore, people diagnosed with SDCA may have a heightened inclination towards intrinsic motivators, such as the desire for personal growth and information acquisition.

Furthermore, the findings demonstrate a significant positive association between SDCA and leadership. When there is a high level of confidence between employees and their leaders, it is more probable that employees will have a sense of empowerment and confidence, enabling them to assume responsibility for their career advancement. Individuals possess a sense of assurance in their ability to obtain equitable treatment, recognition for their efforts, and opportunities for personal growth.

The findings indicate a significant association between leadership and EJS. There exists a positive correlation between leadership competence within an organization and the presence of psychological safety. Additionally, the perception that one's efforts will be acknowledged and appreciated is a contributing factor to overall job satisfaction. The

presence of job satisfaction has been found to influence individuals' loyalty towards their respective organizations positively.

Conclusion

In summary, the prevalence of disruption and disorder characterizes contemporary career trajectories, significantly influencing individuals and organizations. There has been a scarcity of scholarly research examining the potential connections between modern professional orientations and environmental justice movements. This study enhances the credibility of the individual and organizational settings of SDCA by including emerging nations for the first time. Organizations must give precedence to the advancement and impact of nascent vocations, both inside their internal processes and in a broader context. Organizations that emphasize emerging professions and the cultivation of strong leadership principles inside the organizational framework aim to promote equal job opportunities and social justice. Employees with a sense of satisfaction derived from their company are inclined to exhibit behaviors that extend beyond their prescribed job duties, making valuable contributions to the organization's overall success.

The relevance and benefits of employing an SDCA approach in the context of EJS are significant in contemporary society. The modern work environment is distinguished by swift technological progress, shifting job responsibilities, and dynamic industries. In the given context, people who exhibit an SDCA are more adept at effectively navigating the changes above through their proactive pursuit of learning opportunities and ability to adapt to novel obstacles. SDCA follows these principles, enabling individuals to assume responsibility for their trajectories, establish their objectives, and make choices consistent with their interests and ambitions. The presence of autonomy can result in increased levels of job satisfaction. In conclusion, it can be said that SDCA holds significant practicality in contemporary society, primarily owing to its unity with the evolving dynamics of the labor landscape, the imperative nature of ongoing education, and the intrinsic value placed on employee autonomy. It increases job satisfaction and enables employees to navigate their careers within a dynamic, efficient, and constantly expanding professional environment.

Organizations should prioritize the development of new professions in order to achieve both individual and organizational objectives. The present study enhances our understanding of the mechanisms and impacts of behavior on human resources, a crucial aspect for the successful management of careers and the formulation of suitable human resources policies (Baruch, 2014). Management must assess the impact of various work layouts and organizational assistance programs on employees' career perceptions.

Limitations and future work

The manuscript's focus on small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) represents a noteworthy constraint, perhaps restricting its applicability to a broader context. This study can also be analyzed within the context of pre- and post-COVID-19 conditions. In order to augment the outcomes of their studies, future researchers may consider using supplementary variables. This inquiry has the potential for expansion by examining many cultural elements.

Theoretical and practical implications

PCA has gained significant attention within Western society. However, it is essential to conduct an investigation of this notion throughout Eastern culture in order to evaluate any variations. This research investigates the current occupation and its impact on both organizations and individuals in a comprehensive manner. This study conducts a comprehensive analysis of many outcomes associated with the SDCA approach that has received less attention in prior research. Furthermore, it sheds light on supplementary variables that may prompt scholars to reassess and scrutinize PCA in light of these elements. This underscores the theoretical importance of the study.

This study aims to support human resource development (HRD) by providing insights into employees' viewpoints toward career progression in emerging career paradigms. The findings of this study have the potential to aid human resource managers in developing policies that align with current career trends. This, in turn, can improve the convenience and suitability of employment for both employees and employers in a fast-evolving environment. Implementing human resource policies that foster new career concepts is a successful strategy for mitigating employee turnover.

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